

ANALYSIS OF THE WRITTEN OUTPUTS OF GRADE SIX PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

This study is focused on enhancing the writing skills of elementary level pupils by determining and categorizing errors in their written outputs, and recognizing the sources of these errors. Descriptive mixed methods were used in this study, involving 126 teachers and 30 pupils in Taysan District as respondents. A questionnaire served as main data gathering tool, while interview and error analysis were used as techniques to substantiate quantitative data. Coding was used and errors were tallied and classified into different categories. Findings revealed that the top writing problems of the pupils are subject-verb agreement and spelling, which suggests issues in grammar and vocabulary. Majority of the errors are classified as intralingual, which points to the ineffectiveness of pupils in applying rules in these areas. In addition, the pupils' lack of exposure to reading materials and lack of skill in applying rules of writing serve as sources of such errors. Teachers use pre- and post-writing activities to a moderate extent, but use to a great extent during-writing activity. From the results, a module was developed as a supplementary tool that contains drills in developing pupils' spelling and grammar skills. The study recommends the provision of targeted writing activities and optimal feedback to reduce the learners' errors in writing.

Keywords: (a) English, Writing Skills (b) Grammatical Errors and Rules, Spelling (c) Error Analysis, Intralingual Errors, Coding (d) Taysan District, Philippines